

Carboxyalkylated Poly (Vinylalcohol) with Chloroacetic Acid and Polystyrenesulphonic Acid as Coagulant Aids in Nile Water Treatment

E. A. HASSAN, M. M. B. EL-SABBAH, F. M. KAMAL, A. S. ABO EL-MAGD,
ABD-ALLA, A. B. BARAKAT and R. M. ISMAIL

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 23 May 1978, revised 12 June 1980, accepted 7 August 1980

The effect of alum and ferric chloride on the turbidity, pH, alkalinity, residual aluminium or iron content and percent of algae removal in Nile Water treatment was investigated. They were also used in the least possible doses together with different amounts of polyelectrolytes such as carboxyalkylated poly vinyl alcohol (P. V. A.) with monochloroacetic acid (P. V. A. M. C. A.), dichloroacetic acid (P. V. A. D. C. A.) or trichloroacetic acid (P. V. A. T. C. A.) polystyrenesulphonic acid (P. S. S. A.) and also their mixtures. Their efficiencies were compared with those of P.V.A. and NaClO 600 SS 1

THE relatively slow water flow in River Nile, and the absence of flood seasons after the building of Saad El-Ali in Aswan have resulted in little clay sedimental particles. The permitted sunlight to penetrate larger depth through water, has promoted the growth of algae and other organisms in varying amounts (enhanced by pollution from industrial wastes and sewage) and affected in some problems such as taste, odor, filter clogging, attachment to plant walls, toxic and hygienic effects.

The process of coagulation with the help of certain chemicals (which precipitate out insoluble, gelatinous flocculants, neutralize charged particles and combine with them) is reported to be more complete and rapid than will plain sedimentation¹. Among the more commonly used coagulants are: aluminium sulphate, ferrous sulphate² together with calcium hydroxide and sodium aluminate³. Polyelectrolytes, such as polyacrylamide^{4,5} polyacrylic acid⁶, sodium polyacrylate, sodium alginate, secondary or tertiary amines, and also quaternary ammonium or sulphonium salts and their mixtures⁷, are claimed as coagulant aids which increase the efficiency of water purification plants.

While many inorganic salts, and natural organic substances such as gums, starches, algin and proteins can be used as flocculants, the synthetic organic water soluble polymers provide stricter control and usually an economic advantage.

The aim of this work was to investigate the validity of certain synthesized polyelectrolytes (mainly P.V.A.M.C.A., P.V.A.D.C.A., P.V.A.T.C.A. and PSSA)^{8,9} as coagulant aids to remove fine turbidity and algae from Nile water, and comparing the results with those of P.V.A and Nalco 600 SS-1.

Experimental

Materials used :

Commercial alum. Aluminium sulphate with the specifications: Aluminium oxide content 16-18%, Ferric oxide content 0.9%, insoluble matter content not more than 1%, and arsenic content not more than 50 ppm.

Ferric chloride. Egyptian product with the specifications: Ferric chloride content 96%; and foreign matter content not more than 1%.

Nalco 600 SS-1, imported from Italy, a viscous liquid, high molecular weight cationic polyelectrolyte. Laboratory tests showed that the pH of 5% solution is 4.05, phosphate about 0.3 mg/L, chlorides as Cl does not exceed 190 gm, l.

Poly (vinyl alcohol), product of Hoechst Company. Its specifications are mentioned elsewhere⁸.

Carboxyalkylated poly (vinyl alcohol) with mono-, di- or trichloroacetic acids, of the following respective capacities: ml equiv/gm polymer 2.53, 2.86 and 2.628⁸.

Polystyrenesulphonic acid, sulphur content 16.3%, capacity 4.4 ml equiv/gm, and pH of 1% solution = 2.7⁹.

Methods :

Jar Test : Laboratory apparatus for determining optimum dosage of coagulating chemicals.

It is a multistirrer apparatus, consists of container $62 \times 16 \times 12$ dimensions, equipped with electric stirrer having 4 vertical bars attached to each other, and switch, to control the number of revolutions per minute. Each bar has a horizontal plate to stir, the tested water in the beaker ($\frac{1}{2}$ - 1 liter capacity) placed in the container. The height of the bars above the beakers is always kept at constant level.

In each run the coagulant was added to the beaker in 4 different doses upon stirring at revolutions of 120 r.p.m. After two minutes, the coagulant aid was added and after another two minutes, the speed slowed down to 40 r.p.m. for 20 min. Stirring was then stopped and the beakers were left 30 min for settling. Aliquots were then taken for study (5 cm below the surface in all measurements).

The used apparatus resembles approximately the field where flash mixer, clarifier and sedimentation zone act as rapid mixing, slow mixing and a period of time for settling respectively.

Turbidity in silica was determined by the help of photoelectric colorimeter "Lichtelectrisches kolorimeter, Model J. Nach Dr. B. Lange, NO. 11051, Berlin".

The total alkalinity as calcium carbonate mg/l was determined by the methyl orange indicator method¹⁰.

A Beckman pH meter, H-2 Model G. pH-value, No. 5809, West Germany, and a glass electrode, were used for measuring the pH-value.

Residual aluminium was determined by the aluminon method¹⁰.

Residual iron was determined by the thiocyanate method¹¹. The algae count was carried out by the help of a special filtering funnel, Heamacytometer slide and a microscope. The filtering funnel conical in shape, made of pyrex or any other strong glass. It is divided into 2 parts, the first which has the conical shape is of 20 cm height and 12 cm in diameter. The second part is a tube of 10 cm long and 2.5 cm in diameter. It's end is fitted with a rubber stopper containing a capillary tube of 2 mm in diameter. The lower end of the funnel is filled with the filtering medium (fine sand with grain size range from 0.08-0.25 mm), 5 cm over the stopper which is covered by a disc of cloth to prevent sand from falling through the capillary tube. The Heamacytometer slide has been previously used for counting algae inspite of the fact that it is not a standard method¹². Enumeration of the concentrated solutions of algae, collected from washing the sand by a known amount of water-free algae, was carried out by counting the number of viable cells in 6 fields using a Heamacytometer slide (Levy ultra plane,

Cly Adams, 1/400 sq. mm, U.S.A.) and expressing the results as unit cells/ml.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Coagulants :

Experiments were carried out to determine the effective doses of alum and ferric chloride on Nile Water treatment.

The validity of poly vinyl alcohol, its carboxy-alkylated product with chloroacetic acid and polystyrenesulphonic acid as coagulants, were investigated.

Quantities of alum, 5 ppm, or ferric chloride, 4 ppm probably were not effective for the floc to appear in appreciable quantities and sizes, so that the values of residual aluminium (0.35 ppm) and iron (0.4 ppm) in the filtered solution were the highest. Further increase in the added doses lead to an increase in floc formation (and consequently coagulation) and in the same time a decrease in the residual aluminium or iron in the filtered solutions. Doses higher than 55 ppm alum or 22 ppm ferric chloride (which seem to be somewhat expensive) cause an increase in the quantities of residual aluminium or iron, accompanied by coloration in case of ferric chloride.

However, in the two cases, the values of turbidity were 3,4 ppm in silica as compared with the initial values (50 and 52) in the raw Nile water. The alkalinity decreases (and the pH tends towards the acidic range) with increasing the dose of alum or ferric chloride. This is due to released H^+ ions to maintain electrical neutrality in the solution. Natural algae, predominantly carry negative charges, as indicated by their shift towards the positive electrode in the electrophoretic apparatus, may accumulate around the positive centers formed in the solution, and their per cent removal was 90% in both cases as shown in Fig. 1.

On the other hand, different doses of poly (vinyl alcohol), its carboxyalkylated product with chloroacetic acid or polystyrenesulphonic acid, as coagulants, produced no appreciable change in the properties of the studied Nile Water.

Effect of Coagulant Aids :

Optimum doses of alum (15 ppm) and ferric chloride (6 ppm) which produced appreciable decrease in turbidity and considerable algae removal (about 50%) in the treated Nile Water were chosen together with different types and doses of coagulant aids, such as Nalco 600 SS-1, P.V.A., its carboxy-alkylated, P.V.A.M.C.A., P.V.A.D.C.A., P.V.A.T.C.A. and PSSA and also their mixtures.

Fig. 1. Effect of aluminium sulphate as coagulant aid (A, B), and ferric chloride (A, B) on turbidity (B) and algae removal (A).

Results given in Fig. 2 show that Nalco 600 SS-1 (1.6 ppm) together with the optimum doses of alum or ferric chloride, was a suitable coagulant aid resulting in about 87.2, 88% algae removal as compared with the maximum doses of only alum (50 ppm) or ferric chloride (22 ppm).

Fig. 2. Effect of Nalco 600SS1 as coagulant aid in presence of aluminium sulphate 15 ppm. (A, B) and ferric Chloride 6 ppm. (A, B) on turbidity and algae removal A, A.

The decrease in residual Fe is greater tending to nearly zero ppm at 1.6 ppm Nalco, whereas the residual Al reaches 5 ppm at the same conditions. Moreover the alkalinity and pH decrease till 140, 7.6 in case of $FeCl_3$ and 142, 7.75 in case of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ at Nalco doses of 0.2 ppm, after which they acquire relative decrease with higher doses of Nalco. The efficient quantities of P.V.A. as coagulant aid in Nile Water treatment were appreciably high (140-160 ppm).

At doses about 2 ppm of P.V.A.M.C.A., P.V.A.D.C.A. and also P.V.A.T.C.A., the respective percents of algae removal in presence of alum, and in

the presence of ferric chloride were 75, 76.7, 85.6, 82.5, 80.0 and 78.3. They were also effective coagulant aids at doses of 4 ppm, creating floc particles of greater density with considerable settling rates. The addition of P.V.A.M.C.A., P.V.A.D.C.A. and P.V.A.T.C.A. lead to algae removal of 90, 98.2, 92.5 in presence of alum, and 92.5 for the three coagulant aids in case of $FeCl_3$. Curves in Fig. 3 represent the values obtained for P.V.A.M.C.A. The respective values of turbidity, pH and residual AL or Fe with the doses of the added P.V.A.M.C.A. (at a dose of 4 ppm) reached about 4, 7.3, 0.05 in case of alum and 5, 7.6, 0.02 in case of ferric chloride. Similar results were obtained in case of P.V.A.D.C.A. and P.V.A.T.C.A.

Fig. 3. Effect of carboxyalkylated poly vinylalcohol with monochloroacetic acid and aluminium sulphate 15 ppm. (A, B) and ferric chloride 6 ppm. (A, B) on turbidity (B, B) and algae removal (A, A).

On the other hand, the increasing per cent of algae removal with the doses of PSSA, reached 90% at 4-5 ppm in case of alum and 92.5% at 3.5-5 ppm in the presence of ferric chloride.

The respective values at 2 ppm were 81.2 and 83.3%. Higher doses lead to an increase in the per cent of algae removal, whereas the residual aluminium or iron was always less than 0.05 ppm accompanied with fragile and tough flocs smaller doses constructed compact and settable flocs. Doses of 4 ppm from mixtures of PSSA and P.V.A.M.C.A., P.V.A.D.C.A. or P.V.A.T.C.A. in equal weights produced percents of algae removal about 94, 93.4 and 94.3 respectively (in presence of alum). At mixture doses of 2 ppm, the respective values of algae removal 85, 86.9 and 86.3% are comparable with those in case of Nalco 600 SS-1.

Because Nile Water varies and fluctuates widely in quality, needed coagulation and flocculation are best determined in practice by trial.

Required coagulant dosage is usually found by Jar tests performed in all laboratory stirring device. Since coagulation depends on so many variables that are themselves interdependent, as many testing parameters as possible are necessary to investigate, by changing one parameter, while the others being kept constant. The experiments were carried out through 2 years from 8/1971 till 8/1973 over a wide range of temperatures from 14-27° and algae count from 6800-15000 units/ml. The beginning of each curve (zero point) represents the state and quality of the raw Nile Water. The experiments were repeated several times and there is no appreciable change in the results.

It is probable that such cationic polyelectrolytes of opposite charge to the algae cause flocculation by reducing the electrokinetic potential of solid surfaces carrying negative charges and lead therefore to coagulation.

Coagulation was therefore improved by such synthesized coagulant aids, that is, substances that increase the critical mass of colloids and speed up coagulation. The validity of such coagulant aids for water with little turbidity like Nile Water after the building of High Dam and the absence of flood seasons is very important since little turbidity may not coagulate as easily as well as water of moderate turbidity.

References

1. H. E. ROBBIT, J. J. DOLAND and J. L. CLEASBY, *Water Supply Engineering*, 6th ed., McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., U.S.A. (1962).
2. L. ZACEK, V. MICHEK and J. VOJTICH, *Vodni Hospodarství*, 1962, **12**, 398; *C. A.*, 1962, **58**, 6574 C.
3. V. KIM, H. F. LAUDWING and W. D. BISHOP, (Eng. Sci. Inc., Arcadia, Calif.), *J. AWWA*, 1965, **57**(3), 327; *C. A.*, 1965, **62**, 14336h.
4. YU. I. VEITSER and L. N. PASKUTSKIYA, *Sbornik Nauch. Rabot. Akad. Komm. Khoz.*, 1960, **1**, 164; *C.A.*, 1962, **56**, 5769.
5. I. K. SKOLBEV, N. V. PADKOPROV and M. F. KHARBOV, *Irkutsku Nauchn. Issled. Inst. Redk. Metallov.*, 1961, **9**, 152; *C. A.*, 1962, **57**, 13462d.
6. Brit Pat., 1966, 1, 023, 914; *C. A.*, 1960, **64**, 17254.
7. N. SHIKAZONA, S. SASSKI and K. NAEDS, (Govt. Chem. Ind. Res. Inst., Tokyo). *Tokyo Kogyo, Shekensho Hokoko*, 1957, **52**, 149; *C. A.*, 1958, **52**, 808 b.
8. E. A. HASSAN and M. M. B. EL-SABBAH, *Egypt. J. Chems.*, 1974, **17**, 489.
9. M. M. B. EL-SABBAH, M.Sc. Dissertation, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar Univ., Cairo (1973).
10. American Public Health Association (APHA); American Water Works Association (AWWA); Federation of Sewage and Industrial Wastes Association (FSIWA). *Standard Method for the Examination of Water; Sewage, and Industrial Wastes Association, Inc.*, New York, 10 ed. (1956).
11. F. R. THEROUX, E. F. FLDRIDGE and W. L. MALMANN, *Laboratory Manual for Chemical and Bacterial Analysis of Water and Sewage*, 3rd ed., McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc., London, (1943).
12. A. E. CHRISTIE, *J. Water Sewage Works*, 1970, **117**, 58.